

A REVIEW ON APPLICATION OF BAYESIAN THEOREM IN BY USING SYNTHESIS REPERTORY IN HOMOEOPATHY.

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ABSTRACT

Bayes' Theorem calculates the likelihood of an event. For diagnostic purposes, conditional probability is also helpful in the medical sciences. By following Bayes' theorem, the scientific value of homoeopathy can be re-evaluated. Bayes theorem suggests that relative incidence should be used instead of absolute occurrence while compiling symptoms to our Materia medica. The Bayes theorem is applicable to both prospective and retrospective research as well as to consensus based on a large number of examples. In experience-based systems, like homoeopathy, confirmation bias is a significant source of erroneous data. This is something that homoeopathic practitioners should be aware of, and long case follow-ups could be able to fix it. However, it may be overcome by analysing rubrics prospectively using likelihood ratio. The absolute grading method of homoeopathic repertories poses a significant danger to reliability (LR). Here, we'll go over the literature that has already been published and the work that has been done to validate the rubrics taken from the existing repertory using the Bayes theorem.

KEYWORDS:

Bayes theorem, Bayesian theorem, Homeopathy, Repertory, Synthesis, Validation, Rubric.

INTRODUCTION:

Repertory is an index, a catalogue of symptoms of Materia Medica, neatly arranged in a practical form and also indicating the relative gradation of drugs, and it greatly facilitates for quick selection of the indicated remedy^[1].

In the era of Dr. Hahnemann, almost 100 medications were successfully proven. It became difficult to keep track of all the symptoms as remedies and proving's expanded, and Master Hahnemann himself was aware of the necessity for indexing of this expanding collection of knowledge. Hahnemann recognised the limitations of the human mind's capacity to recall every symptom and recognised the need for a tool to help him locate the information^[1].

He demonstrated the procedure by working on cases in Materia Medica Pura, which gave some idea about his concept on which repertorization stands today. He wrote in Materia Medica Pura that for the convenience of treatment, we require writing down all remedies producing a symptom along with the circumstances under which they occur, expressing the remedies in short with few letters and proceed in same way with all other symptoms. From the list thus prepared, we shall be able to perceive the remedy sought for, which covers homoeopathically most of the symptoms, especially characteristic totality^[1].

Synthesis repertory is the enlarged repertory of Kent, also present in Homoeopathic software program Radar. This repertory is edited by Dr. Frederick Schroyens in collaboration with leading Homoeopaths throughout the world and forwarded by George Vithoulkas and also by editor. As this software program consists of new additions, remedies, rubrics. Also new versions and editions are being added^[1].

In 9.1 versions of synthesis repertory in RADAR software total 3,00,000 new remedy references and more than one million rubrics are present.

- Total 14,000 cross-references and 8,000 synonyms are present.
- More than 7,000 new symptoms from Vithoukas clinical practice and Farokh Master's clinical bedside tips,
- Over 10,000 symptoms from the works of Jan Scholtan and also new information from Andre Saine (Canada) having more than 3,200 clinical information.
- W.Boericke Materia medica symptoms from the discription of the characteristic of the mind section.
- It also consist of Julion Materia Medica of the nosodes
- Master Farokh clinical observation of children's remedies (More than 10,600 addition) from almost 886 sources
- Additions of three new chapters - Outer neck and throat. Urinary organs, Genitalia and sexuality. This repertory covers 2373 remedies and in previous version 2277 remedies, which are graded into four grades^[1].

But as the repertories are expanding we should re-evaluate the rubrics and remedies given against them. Because recent studies have shown that there are mistakes in gradation of the remedies in many repertories which can lead to wrong prescription. So the remedies can be validated in statistical manner, this can be done using Bayesian theorem^[1].

Thomas Bayes, a British mathematician, is honoured with the Moniker Bayes' Theorem. The conditional probability is calculated using a mathematical formula. Conditional probability is the possibility that any result will occur depending on the occurrence of a comparable outcome in the past. It provides a mechanism to update previous hypotheses or forecasts with a newly collected data^[2].

Hence by using the data, Bayes' Theorem calculates the likelihood of an event. For diagnostic purposes, conditional probability is also helpful in the medical sciences.

Studies shows that to identify which medicines are suggested if a symptom is present, as well as how strong the indication is, we should continue to update repertories regularly utilising LR rather than haphazard observations. While bias will always exist in many forms, methodical research has the potential to reduce it.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study was to compile and analyse the research that has been published on the use of the Bayesian theorem to validate the rubrics from current repositories.

Search Strategy: Several databases, including PubMed, Google Scholar, MEDLINE, and Science Direct, were utilised to access all of the existing material, including books and scientific data.

DISCUSSION

When RCT evidence falls short to meet the needs of the specific patient, then homoeopathy has a unique chance to establish its own scientific identity and achieve evidence-based customised care. We can make advantage of validated scientific techniques gained from observational study. There is an increasing understanding that prognosis is more important than diagnosis.

The prognosis is a likelihood that the medication will be effective, not a guarantee that it will be superior to a placebo in the majority of patients. Scientific tools like hypothesis testing are required for evaluating probabilities. To achieve this, we can use Bayes' theorem, which is quickly being accepted in all branches of science and is a component of many computer software, particularly expert systems. Increasing numbers of researchers are aware that the Bayes theorem is a fundamental idea in medical knowledge. Details of the previously studies are discussed in the (Table. 1).

Table. 1. Studies related to Bayesian Theorem

Title	Design	Objective	Sample size	Result	Conclusion
<p>Study the importance of validation of rubrics by Bayesian theorem through complete repertory^[3].</p>	<p>Single arm non randomized trial</p>	<p>The primary objective was to see the utility of LR for prior & posterior probability of work of medicines.</p>	<p>30</p>	<p>1)Marked - More than 75% disappearance of symptoms 2) Moderate - Patient has symptomatic relief with more than 50% reduction 3)Mild- when the patients has symptomatic relief with less than 50% reduction.</p>	<p>Total 12 rubrics were validated using bayes theorem. In this study a accurate role of validation of rubrics for selecting of simillimum with Repertorisat ion was done.</p>
<p>A Bayesian perspective on the reliability of homeopathic repertories^[4].</p>	<p>Single arm non randomized trial</p>	<p>Absolute grading of the medicines in rubrics should be replaced by relative grading.</p>	<p>1634 patients had been taken out of which 1049 prescriptions were evaluated.</p>	<p>The rubric " Fear of death " & "loquacity" were more defective than compared to other 2 rubrics i.e., "Grinding of teeth during sleep" & "Herpes lips".</p>	<p>During the study many flaws were present in the Kent's Repertory. By the use of Bayes' theorem repertory is improved.</p>

<p>A Retrospective clinical evaluation of the rubrics using likelihood ratio in cases with good therapeutic response to arsenic album^[5].</p>	<p>Retrospective study</p>	<p>To verify and evaluate the medicines present in the rubric.</p>	<p>Total 1360 records were taken out of which 642 records were evaluated.</p>	<p>Total 17 rubrics were verified. LR+ with 95% confidence Interval & LR- with 95% confidence Interval were calculated in this study.</p>	<p>By Retrospective verification of the symptom it can help in selecting the symptoms for a prospective study.</p>
<p>Prospective evaluation of few homeopathic rubrics of Kent's repertory from Bayesian perspective^[6]</p>	<p>Single arm non randomized trial</p>	<p>To evaluate few rubrics of Kent's Repertory by prospective study.</p>	<p>Total 2039 prescriptions were analysed.</p>	<p>Total 13 rubrics were validated. Presence of a symptom was graded on the basis of degrees 0 = absent, 1 = mild/less intense & 2 = strong.</p>	<p>The relative grading without giving statistical uncertainties was a problem so to overcome those LR are calculated.</p>
<p>Retrospective estimation of prevalence and likelihood ratio of general symptoms of 29 less frequently prescribed homeopathic medicines by clinical verification^[7].</p>	<p>Retrospective study</p>	<p>The purpose of this study is to determine the prevalence & LR's of general symptoms in 29 less commonly prescribed Homeopathic medicines.</p>	<p>Total 4652 records were taken for analysis.</p>	<p>LR's & confined LR'S >1.5 were elicited for 6 & 49 symptoms, respectively, out of 166 general symptoms of 29 medicines.</p>	<p>In spite of considerable caveats, this study is the first insight into prevalence & LR's of general symptoms of less frequently prescribed homeopathic medicines.</p>

<p>Statistical analysis of six repertory rubrics after prospective assessment applying Bayes' theorem^[8].</p>	<p>Single arm non randomized trial</p>	<p>To statistically verify six rubrics from Kents repertory by application of Bayes' theorem.</p>	<p>Total 4094 patients were enrolled out of which 4072 prescriptions were analysed.</p>	<p>After converting typeface to LR's the probability of existing repertory entries compared to their findings were calculated, our analysis produced 121 relevant results for validating existing repertory entries. Total 55 rubrics were verified.</p>	<p>Our LR analysis confirms that commonly used medications are overrepresented in the repertory.</p>
<p>Bayes' theorem: scientific assessment of experience^[9].</p>	<p>Observational study</p>	<p>Importance in application of bayes theorem in both prospective & retrospective study.</p>	<p>–</p>	<p>Notwithstanding its limits, bayesian assessment of homoeopathic symptom is practical & is required for the advancement of Homoeopathy.</p>	<p>Baye's theorem, which compares the population that responds well to a given homoeopathic medicine to the rest of the population, should be kept in the mien when evaluating all available data from various resources.</p>

<p>Prognostic factor research in homoeopathy^[10].</p>	<p>Observational study</p>	<p>Validation of homeopathic medicines is about validating effectiveness in individual cases.</p>	<p>–</p>	<p>More scientific tools beyond hypothesis testing are required to determine probabilities - For this aim, we can use Bayes' theorem, which is widely accepted in all branches of science.</p>	<p>The rise of individualised chance for homoeopathy to forge its own scientific identity that will serve as a model for all medications.</p>
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CONCLUSION

A tradition of individualized medicine exists in homoeopathy. The rise of individualised medicine in conventional healthcare presents homoeopathy with an excellent opportunity to build its own unique scientific identity that is representative of all medications.

The current method of adding symptoms to our Materia medica based on their absolute occurrence in proving's or successful cases is no longer appropriate because it will result in a large number of incorrect entries in our repertories. By using Bayes' theory, we may address this flaw and give homoeopathy a scientific analysis. While evaluating all available data from various sources, Bayes' theorem should be kept in mind because it compares the population that responds favourably to a particular homoeopathic treatment with the rest of the population.

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